

Thermal, magnetic, ESR and antibacterial study of some Schiff base metal complexes

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Complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with the Schiff bases formed by condensation of 2-aminopyridine with 2-furfuraldehyde, ethyl methyl ketone and salicylaldehyde of the general formulae $(\text{ML}_2)\cdot\text{Cl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $(\text{ML}_2)\cdot\text{Cl}_2$ and $(\text{ML}_2)\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been synthesized. Ligand field parameters of some of the complexes have been calculated. The complexes have been screened for their antibacterial activities.

Schiff base metal complexes have been widely studied because of their industrial and biological applications¹. Several derivatives of 2-aminopyridine, furan, ethyl methyl ketone and their derivatives are being used as drugs². The present investigation aims at the synthesis and antimicrobial studies of 2-furfurylidene-2-aminopyridine (FAP), ethyl methyl ketone-2-aminopyridine (EMKAP), salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (SAP) Schiff bases and their metal chelates with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} .

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes of FAP, EMKAP and SAP (Table 1) indicate metal-to-Schiff base ratio to be 1 : 2. The complexes are stable in air, non-hygroscopic and soluble in DMF, acetone and methanol. The conductivity data of the complexes (in 10^{-3} M methanol) show 1 : 2 electrolytic nature for FAP and EMKAP-metal complexes, and non-electrolytic nature for SAP-metal complexes.

The FAP-ligand-IR band at 1630 cm^{-1} (C=N) shifts to lower frequency region ($1610 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in all the three complexes indicating the participation of this group in chelation³. A medium intensity ligand band is observed at 1125 cm^{-1} (C–O–C)^{3,4}. On coordination of ring oxygen with the metal ion, this band position shifts to $1158 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The new bands at 515 ± 10 and $425 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ metal complexes have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ mode respectively⁵.

The EMKAP-ligand band at 1623 cm^{-1} (C=N) shifts to $1608 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on complexation, suggesting participation of azomethine group on complexation³. Pyridine shows an absorption bands at 3130, 1480 and 1040 cm^{-1} (ring nitrogen). These bands show positive shift by 15–25 cm^{-1} in the complexes, which suggests participation of pyridynyl

nitrogen on complexation⁶. The band at $430 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ mode.

The SAP-ligand band at 1588 cm^{-1} (C=N) on chelation shifts to lower frequency ($1560 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$), suggesting participation of azomethine group on complexation. The ligand spectrum shows bands at 3177 and 1351 cm^{-1} due to the stretching vibration and phenolic OH deformation, which are absent in the spectra of the complexes. An intense ligand band at 1278 cm^{-1} (phenolic C–O) shifts to higher frequency ($1290 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes. These suggest deprotonation of the phenolic OH group after its chelation with the metal ion⁷.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} -FAP complex shows one band at 15900 cm^{-1} (ν_3) which have been assigned to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition. The magnetic moment value (4.01 B.M.) suggests its tetrahedral geometry. The Ni^{II} -complex gives two bands at 13028 and 18552 cm^{-1} , these are tentatively assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ (ν_1) and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ (ν_2) transitions. This in association with diamagnetic nature of the complex suggest the geometry to be square-planar. Two absorption bands at 12515 and 19230 cm^{-1} in the Cu^{II} complex are tentatively assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions. This is in favour of the square-planar geometry^{8–10}.

The EMKAP- Co^{II} complex shows band at 16100 cm^{-1} which is assigned to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition. The tetrahedral geometry has been suggested for this complex. The Ni^{II} complex gives three bands at 15100, 18115 and 21100 cm^{-1} , corresponding to transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$, respectively. It is diamagnetic and therefore square-planar geometry has been suggested. The Cu^{II} complex gives band at 12315 and 17513 cm^{-1} , which

are assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions. This favours the square-planar geometry.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd.	Colour/ M.p. °C	Metal % : Found/ (Calcd.)	Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
FAP	Black 80	—	—	—
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ O) ₂]. Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Brown 100	11.35 (11.55)	186.0	4.01
[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ O) ₂]. Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Brown 95	11.53 (11.51)	163.0	diamag.
[Cu(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ O) ₂]. Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Brown 95	12.00 (12.34)	172.0	1.89
EMKAP	Brown 90	—	—	—
[Co(C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂) ₂].Cl ₂	Blue 210	13.62 (13.82)	115.0	4.10
[Ni(C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂) ₂].Cl ₂	Green 203	13.76 (13.78)	127.0	diamag.
[Cu(C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂) ₂].Cl ₂	Green 213	14.65 (14.75)	135.0	1.95
SAP	Yellow 95	—	—	—
[Co(C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ O) ₂]. 3H ₂ O	Green 202	11.61 (11.66)	18.0	5.01
[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ O) ₂]. 3H ₂ O	Green 211	11.65 (11.63)	34.0	3.03
[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₂ O) ₂]. 3H ₂ O	Brown 200	12.33 (12.46)	25.0	2.05

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

The SAP-Co^{II} complex gives band at 14531 and 19455 cm^{-1} , assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively. The values of ligand field parameters $10 Dq$, B , β , LFSE and λ are 10360 cm^{-1} , 1024 cm^{-1} , 0.91, 99.1 kJ mol^{-1} and $(-)$ 745 cm^{-1} , respectively, favour an octahedral geometry for this complex. The three bands at 11325, 19326 and 23115 cm^{-1} in the Ni^{II} complex are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively. The values of ligand field parameters $10 Dq$, B , β , LFSE and λ are 11327 cm^{-1} , 564 cm^{-1} , 0.54, 162.4 kJ mol^{-1} and $(-)$ 145 cm^{-1} , respectively, which favour the octahedral geometry for the complex. The Cu^{II} complex gives broad band at 12658–16393 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to transition ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$. The value of ligand field parameters $10 Dq$, λ and LFSE are 15148 cm^{-1} , $(-)$ 788 cm^{-1} and 108.97 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively, favouring an octahedral geometry for this complex^{10,12}.

The TGA curve of FAP-Ni^{II} complex shows its decomposition start at 60°. The lattice water comes out at 130–150° (% wt.-loss, 8.00/7.03); this weight-loss corresponds to two molecules of lattice water. The thermal degradation

of the Schiff base and chloride moiety from the metal chelate begins above 150° and the pyrolysis curve exhibits this process to occur in two steps, the first at 150–400° and the second at 400–560°. After 560° the pyrolysis curve shows the continuous loss of ligand. A horizontal thermal curve has been observed after 630° in this complex. The percentage weight of the residue (obs./calc., 16.95/14.40) corresponds to nickel oxide, the ultimate pyrolysis product¹¹.

The decomposition of EMKAP-Co^{II} complex starts at 200°. The curve shows absence of lattice as well as coordinated water. The thermal degradation of the Schiff base and chloride moiety from the metal chelate begins above 200° and the pyrolysis curve exhibits this process to occur in two steps. The remaining part of the ligands in the coordination sphere break in two steps, the first at 200–300° (% wt.-loss 17.00/16.67) and the second at 300–600°. A horizontal thermal curve has been observed after 600°. The percentage weight of the residue (obs./calc. 25.00/17.38), corresponds to the cobalt oxide as an ultimate pyrolysis product.

ESR spectra of FAP-Cu and EMKAP-Cu complexes recorded on X-band at frequency 9.07 GHz under the magnetic field strength of 2000 ± 4000 and 3000 ± 2000 gauss at temperature 30° exhibit Lorentzian type of peaks. The values of ESR parameters for FAP-Cu complex, viz, g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} , G and Δg are as 2.0705, 1.9452, 1.9869, 1.2075 and 0.1253, respectively, and the corresponding values for EMKAP-Cu complex are 2.0750, 1.9225, 1.9739, 0.8292, 0.1523. The value of g_{\parallel} for both the complexes indicate the prevalence of covalent character in the metal-ligand bond. The value of axial symmetry parameter G for these complexes are appreciably less than 4 which indicates the strong-field nature of the ligands. The value of $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ in these complexes suggests the square-planar geometry^{8,12}.

Antibacterial activity : All the three Schiff bases and their metal complexes have been evaluated for their antibacterial activity against *S. typhi*, *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* at concentrations 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ by single disc method¹³. The Cu^{II} complexes show higher activity than the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. Metal complexes are more active than the Schiff base^{13,14}.

Experimental

The Schiff bases (FAP, EMKAP and SAP) were synthesized by refluxing a mixture of an equimolar amount of 2-aminopyridine with 2-furfuraldehyde/ethylmethyl ketone/salicylaldehyde in methanolic medium on a water-bath for 5–7 h. The resulting products were crystallized from methanol.

The metal complexes were prepared by adding a

methanolic solution of the respective metal salt ($MCl_2 \cdot nH_2O$) to a methanolic solution of the Schiff base (FAP, EMKAP or SAP) in 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio and refluxing the mixture on a water-bath for 4–6 h. The resulting coloured complexes were washed with methanol and petroleum ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator and further in an electric oven at 80°. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel.

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